

**EXAMINING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN WORK EXPERIENCE,
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A CORRELATIONAL STUDY**

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Examining the Relationship between Work Experience, Educational Background, and Employability: A Correlational Study

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between work experience, educational background, and employability. Utilizing a correlational research design, a researcher-developed questionnaire was administered to a sample of 151 human resources practitioners from the National Capital Region (NCR) through cluster sampling. The research instrument's validity and reliability were evaluated by assessing content and construct validity, along with calculating the reliability coefficient using Cronbach's alpha to establish its psychometric properties. Also, interviews were conducted to triangulate the findings and enhance the study's rigor, addressing potential social desirability and response biases inherent in self-reported data from online surveys. Pearson R Correlation Analysis assessed the strength and direction of the linear relationships among these variables. The results indicated that employers prioritize work experience over educational background in hiring decisions. Specifically, there is a low but significant positive relationship between the preference for work experience and the likelihood of applicants being hired, as well as between the preference for educational background and employment probability. These findings suggest that job seekers might enhance their employability by acquiring relevant work experience and that hiring practices could benefit from placing greater emphasis on practical experience. Thus, the study acknowledges limitations including the use of simple random sampling and the geographic focus on the National Capital Region, which may affect the generalizability of the findings.

Keywords: *work experience, educational background, applicants' probability of getting hired*

Introduction

The corporate world's ongoing debate centers on the relative importance of education versus experience for employment. This contention involves fresh graduates and seasoned employees, with organizations often setting minimum educational requirements (e.g., a high school diploma or bachelor's degree) for job positions to assess fit and prevent job mismatches (Indeed, 2021). While education provides a foundational qualification, work experience, defined as previous engagement in similar job roles, is frequently deemed crucial. The debate persists, with some advocating for the primacy of experience and others for educational qualifications as the key criterion for hiring decisions.

Harvard Business School's studies (2010, 2017) revealed that a bachelor's degree is often a mandatory requirement for job listings, reflecting employers' perception that degree holders are better prepared for job roles. This requirement has intensified in the 21st century, with some employers even favoring candidates pursuing or holding master's degrees. Despite this trend, a degree undeniably provides a competitive edge in the job market, offering numerous opportunities. Education aims to equip individuals with the necessary skills and knowledge for various professional and life activities, especially in a highly competitive job market. While some prioritize workplace experience over formal education, the disadvantages of this preference often outweigh the benefits, as experience enhances the likelihood of employment across various fields (Anyangwe, 2012).

Addressing the persistent undervaluation of education in the workplace is crucial, especially given the limited comprehensive scholarly literature on the hiring preferences of Filipino employers. Understanding employers' valuation of education and experience is vital as the corporate landscape evolves. The debate extends to the employer's preference for education versus experience, often depending on the nature of the work and recruitment managers' preferences. Recent surveys and studies indicate a growing emphasis on higher education in hiring decisions, with significant service length also being a critical factor (Finley, 2021; AAC&U, 2018).

This study delves deeper into the recruitment and selection issues, exploring the correlation between educational background, work experience, and applicants' hiring probability. The findings aim to inform the selection criteria for specific job positions, offering employers strategies for prioritizing education or work experience and their impact on hiring probabilities. The study also seeks to enhance the quality of service and productivity in organizations by identifying the qualifications that best fit job positions. Additionally, it provides insights into the strengths and drawbacks of considering educational and work experience during recruitment, contributing to future research on employer preferences. The study highlights the increasing job competition and the necessity for employers to have competent, experienced employees, which are crucial for organizational success (Bhatt & Jain, 2015; Advanced Group, 2019).

As established by Torpey (2021), academic achievement correlates with higher earnings and lower unemployment rates, emphasizing the importance of higher education for career starters. As careers progress, work experience and the acquisition of new skills gain prominence. This research is timely and relevant, offering benefits to employers by enabling them to adopt various strategies and perceptions in hiring employees. By re-evaluating their hiring efforts, employers can align with industry needs and workforce demands.

Utilizing simple random sampling and surveys, this study aims to understand employers' preferences between education and experience and their correlation with applicants' hiring probabilities. This comprehensive approach will provide reliable insights into the labor market's best practices, with the research expected to span nine to ten months.

Research Questions

This study examined the relationship between work experience, educational background, and employability. Additionally, it sought to quantify the relationship between employers' preferences for educational qualifications and work experience and the probability of applicants being hired. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. In terms of employee selection, which among educational background and work experience do employers prefer the most?
2. Is there a significant relationship between the employer's degree of preference for work experience and their applicants' probability of getting hired?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the employer's degree of preference for educational background and their applicants' probability of getting hired?

Literature Review

Employers' Hiring and Selection Preferences

Recent scientific studies have explored employers' typical hiring and selection preferences in the industrial sector. Researchers have identified various recruitment strategies used by employers, with much of the research focusing on employment management and labor issues in the corporate sector.

General Employment Conditions in the Philippines

According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA, 2021), the employment rate in January 2021 was 91.3%, a decrease from 94.7% in January 2020. The Department of Labor and Employment (2014) stated that the minimum wage in the National Capital Region (NCR) is 547 pesos per day, with standard working hours set at eight hours per day, including breaks. Overtime must be compensated. Despite these regulations, significant disparities in wages between NCR and other regions persist, highlighting the need for more equitable salary policies.

Recruitment and Selection Trends

Thurston (2021) noted that recruitment trends evolve annually, with post-pandemic recruitment practices becoming obsolete. In 2022, job seekers were more selective, recognizing that their skills are highly sought after by employers. This shift necessitates that employers adapt their recruitment strategies to attract top talent.

Strategies for Recruiting and Selecting Prospective Workers

Rabha (2021) suggested several strategies for attracting talented job applicants, including employee referral programs, where organizations reward employees for successful referrals. Additionally, positioning employees as brand ambassadors can reduce advertising costs and attract top talent. Courting talented applicants with personalized benefits and perks can further enhance recruitment efforts.

Basic Employment Qualifications in Recruiting and Selecting Employees

Doyle (2020) outlined essential employment qualifications in the U.S., including authorization to work, obtaining a U.S. Work Visa, a green card, a working permit, and a Social Security Number. These qualifications ensure legal eligibility to work and are crucial for securing employment.

The Interplay Between Education and Employment

Wood et al. (2018) discussed the evolving labor market and the importance of qualifications in employment. Studies by Furlong et al. (2017), Wood et al. (2019), and Wyn et al. (2017) highlighted the challenges young females face in securing stable employment despite significant educational investments. This underscores the constrained relationship between education and employment, particularly in the gig economy.

Work Experience in Employment

Rowe (2017) emphasized the role of work experience in enhancing students' employability. His model of work-integrated learning highlights the impact of individual (skills and social skills) and contextual factors (work environment) on work experience. Beam and Quimbo (2021) found that short-term employment increases youth employment rates in the Philippines, with students without work experience benefiting from being reliable candidates.

Experience-Related Work Qualifications in Foreign Countries

Pollard (2019) reported that 65% of UK employers consider relevant work experience crucial in the hiring process. Shakhshir (2022)

found that 37% of HR practitioners favor work experience over educational attainment, predicting future job success based on work experience.

Education-Based Qualifications

Regis College (2022) highlighted the importance of a bachelor's degree for many employers, offering advantages such as lower unemployment rates and solid core competencies (Kaushal, 2020). Raman (2017) discussed degree inflation, where job postings increasingly require a college degree. Shulman (2019) found a positive correlation between educational attainment and hiring probability, suggesting that higher education contributes to business success.

Synthesis

Extensive research has examined employers' preferences for educational background and work experience in hiring decisions. Most literature favors work experience over educational background, but little research has explored the specific length of work experience valued by employers. Some studies indicate a preference for educational background. However, there is limited investigation into the correlation between employers' preferences for these qualifications and the probability of hiring applicants. Future research should survey the preferred length of work experience and educational background levels, examining the correlation between these preferences and hiring probabilities. Developing psychometrically sound assessment instruments to evaluate employers' preferences and their impact on hiring decisions is also recommended.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized a quantitative correlational design to examine the relationship between work experience, educational background, and employability. This approach enabled the researchers to quantify the strength and direction of associations between these variables. By analyzing the data through statistical methods, the study aimed to provide empirical evidence on how work experience and educational qualifications influence the probability of being hired.

Participants

This study gathered data from 151 Filipino human resource practitioners with at least three years of experience in employee recruitment, hiring, and selection. The study did not specify an age bracket or job position, as long as the respondents had relevant experience in the Human Resource Department. To obtain the target sample, the researchers utilized cluster sampling, dividing the population into clusters based on regions or organizations, and then randomly selecting respondents from these clusters.

Instrument

Researcher-made Questionnaire

The study used a researcher-made questionnaire in gathering important data from the target respondents in an efficient manner, which helped the researchers achieve the result of their study. For good measure, the researchers analyzed existing psychometric instruments derived from various academic studies related to employers' value proposition in preferred hiring qualifications with regard to the educational background and work experience and applicants' probability of getting hired to develop a comprehensive questionnaire as a research instrument.

In gathering information and relevant answers from each respondent, the researchers created their own research questionnaire, divided into four sections. The first part contains thirteen (13) demographic questions titled the "Qualifications of Respondent and Preference for Job Application, which thus include preferred recruitment qualifications, which will be measured using a checklist. This particular section in the instrument also aims to determine which of the two prevalent recruitment qualifications (i.e., educational background and work experience) the majority of employers' value more in the corporate world. The second part of the instrument entitled "Employers' Preference for Educational Background (EPEB)", on the other hand, contains a set of (20) 4-point Likert scale-based questions that evaluates the degree of preference for educational background, as a good predictor of a job applicant's work performance. Meanwhile the third part of the instrument entitled "Employers' Preference for Work Experience (EPWE)" which comprises twenty (20) questions and employs a 4-point Likert scale whereas this instrument assesses the degree of preference for work experience as a good predictor of a job applicant's work experience. Lastly, the fourth part of the instrument contains thirty (30) questions that will also utilize a 4-point Likert Scale entitled "Probability of a Job Applicant for Getting Hired by the Employer" this instrument helps assess the employer's prospects of the probability of a certain candidate being accepted into the organization.

It is also worth mentioning that the research instrument was designed by the researchers according to the 4-point Likert Scale. The research team also adapted Rensis Likert's interpretation table for a four-point Likert scale. Subsequently, the questionnaire undertook validated by three licensed psychometricians, with considerable expertise in human resource management, or who also worked as an HR practitioner. The three licensed psychometricians sought to verify that this instrument was used as a basis for obtaining important data from the respondents, according to its psychometric aspects. To fully interpret the research data, the researchers used different types of statistical analysis, such as descriptive and inferential statistics. According to statistical analysis, the research instrument's

reliability coefficient is $\alpha = 96.8\%$, indicating that the survey's ability to produce similar or consistent results is of exceptional quality. The researchers have also determined the content validity index of the instrument based on the ratings that the subject-matter experts have given per item. It revealed that the instrument's total content validity index is 0.82. The items shown with a content validity index of 0.82 for three research experts could be considered evidence of good content validity.

Semi-structured Interview Guide

A semi-structured interview guide was developed to triangulate the study's findings and enhance its rigor by mitigating potential social desirability and response biases associated with self-reported data from online surveys. This interview guide was meticulously validated by subject matter experts to ensure its relevance and accuracy in capturing comprehensive insights. By incorporating expert feedback, the guide was refined to effectively address the nuanced aspects of participants' experiences and perceptions, thereby providing a more robust and credible data set.

Procedure

To examine the relationship between work experience, educational background, and employability, a comprehensive research instrument was developed. This instrument comprised a four-part questionnaire, which was validated by three licensed psychometricians with expertise in human resources management. The psychometric quality of the instrument was further assessed through reliability analysis using Cronbach's alpha and validation of content and construct validity based on expert ratings. Additionally, a semi-structured interview guide was created to triangulate findings and enhance the study's rigor, addressing potential biases related to social desirability and response tendencies inherent in self-reported data from online surveys.

The study was conducted over a period of three months, with data collection occurring within one month. The research instrument was administered online to a sample of 151 Filipino employers in the National Capital Region (NCR). To facilitate data collection, a Google form link was included in publication materials distributed via social media platforms (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Gmail). This approach was necessitated by the COVID-19 pandemic, which limited traditional data collection methods. Informed consent was meticulously obtained from all participants, ensuring they were well-informed about the study's purpose, risks, benefits, and the voluntary nature of their participation. Written consent was secured prior to data collection. To further validate the results, interviews were conducted to complement the survey data and mitigate biases. Pearson-r correlation analysis was employed to evaluate the strength and direction of linear relationships among variables. Prior to finalizing the report, the research paper underwent a thorough review by the researchers to correct any typographical or grammatical errors, ensuring precision and thoroughness in the presentation of findings.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers adhered to strict ethical standards to prevent plagiarism by ensuring that all sources, works, and data from other professionals were properly cited and acknowledged, thereby attributing credit appropriately to original contributors. Participant data were securely stored in protected systems, with stringent measures in place to prevent unauthorized access or disclosure. This approach safeguarded the confidentiality of personal information throughout the research process.

Moreover, informed consent was systematically obtained from all participants at the commencement of data collection. Both during pilot testing and the actual study, participants signed consent forms to confirm their voluntary participation and permission for the use of their data, including company-specific information such as names and locations. The researchers also ensured the integrity of reported results by avoiding any misuse or distortion of data. All findings were reported accurately and transparently, with no selective omission, alteration, or fabrication of data. Any errors identified during the reporting process were rigorously addressed and corrected to maintain the study's credibility.

Results and Discussion

This presents the results, the analysis, and interpretation of data gathered from the answers to the questionnaires distributed to the field. The said data were presented in tabular form in accordance with the specific questions posited in the statement of the problem.

Table 1. Means and Standard Deviations of Educational Background and Work Experience

<i>Employers' Preference</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>
Educational Background	151	3.2116	0.7217
Work Experience	151	3.2937	0.6922

Table 1 presented the mean and standard deviation values for educational background and work experience. The mean score for educational background was 3.2116 (SD = 0.7217), indicating a strong preference among employers for educational background as a predictor of job performance. Similarly, the mean score for work experience was 3.2937 (SD = 0.6922), reflecting a robust preference for work experience as a predictor of job performance.

Table 2. Means and Standard Deviation of Probability of The Job Applicants Getting Hired

<i>Rate of the Employers'</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>
Probability of Getting Hired	151	3.4662	0.5683

Table 2 presented the mean and standard deviation of the probability of job applicants being hired, as assessed by employers. The analysis yielded a mean score of 3.4662 (SD = 0.5683), indicating a high level of perceived likelihood that job applicants would be hired. This result demonstrates that employers generally perceived a strong probability of job candidates securing employment.

Table 3. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution in terms of Employers' Preferred Requirement Qualification*

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Educational Background	69	45.7	45.7	45.7
Work Experience	82	54.3	54.3	100.0
Total	151	100.0	100.0	

Table 3 presented the frequency and percentage distribution of employers' preferred qualifications for job applicants. The data indicated that 82% of human resources practitioners preferred candidates with work experience (N = 151, f = 82). In contrast, only 45.7% of practitioners prioritized educational background as a preferred qualification (N = 151, f = 69). Consequently, the researchers concluded that work experience was the most favored employment qualification among Filipino employers when selecting job applicants for their organizations.

Table 4. *Regression Analysis of Work Experience and Employability*

Change Statistics							
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	F	df1
1	.486	.236	.231	.32651	.236	46.059	1

Table 4 presented the results of the regression analysis examining the relationship between employers' preference for work experience and employability. The findings indicated a low positive correlation ($r = .486$, $r^2 = .236$, adjusted $r^2 = .231$) between the extent of employers' preference for work experience as a hiring criterion and the employability of job applicants. This correlation reflects the degree to which employers' emphasis on work experience influences the likelihood of applicants being hired.

Table 5. *Results of Hypothesis Testing for the First Null Hypothesis of the Study*

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	Probability of Job Applicants Getting Hired	2.259	.180		12.559	.000
	Degree of Preference for Work Experience	.367	.054	.486	6.787	.000

*** If p-value is less than 0.05, Reject Null hypothesis (R-Value = 0.486; F- Value = 46.059; P- Value = 0.000)

Table 5 illustrated that the rate of job applicants' employability and the employers' degree of preference for work experience both yielded significance levels of $p=0.000$. As these values were both below the threshold of $p=0.05$, the null hypothesis was rejected. Consequently, a significant relationship was identified between employers' preference for work experience and job applicants' employability.

Table 6. *Results of Hypothesis Testing for the Second Null Hypothesis of the Study*

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1. Regression	4.910	1	4.910	46.059	.000b
Residual	15.885	149	.107		
Total	20.796	150			

*** If p-value is less than 0.05, Reject Null hypothesis (R-Value = 0.486; F- Value = 46.059; P- Value = 0.000)

H2: *There is no significant difference between the employer's degree of preference for work experience and the job applicant's employability.*

Table 6 illustrated the relationship between work experience and applicants' employability as perceived by employers. The analysis yielded an F-value of 46.059 with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, based on numerator degrees of freedom (df) = 1 and denominator df = 149. This p-value, being significantly lower than the alpha level of 0.05, led to the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating a statistically significant difference between the employers' preference for work experience and applicants' employability.

Table 7. *Regression Analysis of Educational Background and the Employability of Applicants*

Change Statistics							
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	F	df1
1	.418	.175	.170	.33931	.175	31.624	1

Table 7 presented the results of the regression analysis examining the relationship between employers' preferences for educational background and the employability of job applicants. The analysis revealed a low positive correlation ($r = .418$, $r^2 = .175$, adjusted r^2

= .170) between employers' overall preference for educational background and the employability of candidates. This indicated that while there is a measurable association between the preference for educational qualifications and employability, the strength of this relationship is relatively modest.

Table 8. Results of Hypothesis Testing for the Third Null Hypothesis of the Study

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	Probability of Job Applicants Getting Hired	2.547	.166		15.361	.000
	Degree of Preference for Educational Background	.286	.051	.418	5.624	.000

*** If p-value is less than 0.05, Reject Null hypothesis (R-Value = 0.418; F-Value = 31.624; P-Value = 0.000)

H3: There is no significant relationship between the employer's degree of preference for educational background and the job applicant's employability.

Table 8 demonstrated that the employability of job applicants, as assessed by employers, exhibited a statistically significant level of $p=0.000$. Similarly, the degree of employers' preference for educational background also revealed a significant level of $p=0.000$. Both p-values were below the $\alpha=0.05$ threshold, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. These results indicate a significant relationship between the employers' preference for educational background and the employability of job applicants.

Table 9. Results of Hypothesis Testing for the Fourth Null Hypothesis of the Study

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.641	1	3.641	31.624	.000b
	Residual	17.155	149	.115		
	Total	20.796	150			

*** If p-value is less than 0.05, Reject Null hypothesis (R-Value = 0.486; F-Value = 31.624; P-Value = 0.000)

H4: There is no significant difference between the employer's degree of preference for educational background and the job applicant's employability.

Table 9 presents the analysis of the difference between the degree of preference for educational background and the employability of applicants. The results indicated a p-value of 0.000, corresponding to an F-value of 31.624 with 1 degree of freedom in the numerator and 149 degrees of freedom in the denominator. The significance level of 0.000, being less than the established threshold ($\alpha = 0.05$), led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Consequently, the findings demonstrate a significant difference between the degree of preference for educational background and the employability of job applicants.

The primary objective of this research was to examine the relationship between work experience, educational background, and employability. The study's findings corroborated those of the 2016 EPS Survey, which indicated that 65% of UK employers deemed relevant work experience crucial, while 38% valued any form of work experience, and 11% prioritized internship experience (Pollard, 2019). Similarly, the 2017 NACE Job Outlook Survey found that over 91% of employers placed significant emphasis on work experience, with 65% preferring relevant experience, 26% any form of experience, and only 5% disregarding it for fresh graduates. This preference for work experience was also noted by Shakhshir (2022), who found that respondents favored work experience over educational qualifications as a predictor of job performance.

These results align with findings from Pollard (2019), Shakhshir (2022), and NACE (2017), which highlighted the predominant role of work experience in the hiring process, suggesting it as a key indicator of job readiness and career ambition. However, other studies, such as those by Heller (2019) and Glazer (2017), argue that work experience alone is not a reliable predictor of job performance and must be considered alongside other factors like education, personality, and skills. Ali and Jalal (2018) and Torpey (2021) emphasized the ongoing importance of educational qualifications, noting that a bachelor's degree correlates with lower unemployment rates and better job preparedness. Fueller and Raman (2017) also argued that educational attainment remains a critical factor for employers, despite the variability in its predictive value.

Conversely, research by Beard (2019) and Helyer and Lee (2014) suggested that work experience does not always correlate with job performance, and that highly experienced candidates may sometimes face challenges adapting to new work environments. This is consistent with findings from Tien (2022), which suggested that experienced applicants may be overlooked due to inflexible work habits. The study's results support the Human Capital Theory (Becker, 1964), which posited that both educational background and work experience are important indicators of an applicant's potential productivity.

Additionally, the study aligned with Shulman (2019) and Tentama and Abdillah (2019), showing a positive correlation between educational background and employability, which indicates that higher education can enhance job prospects. However, Coupe, Vakhitova, and Sologoub (2014) found that in some contexts, such as Vietnam, education alone may not significantly improve employment prospects, suggesting a need for educational reforms. Overall, the research supported the notion that both education and work experience are integral to assessing job candidates, as reflected in the "Recruitment Theory" (Winston, 2007) and Schneider's

(1987) Attraction-Selection-Attrition model, highlighting the necessity for a comprehensive evaluation of multiple qualifications in the hiring process.

The results of the study revealed that employers place a higher priority on work experience compared to educational background when making hiring decisions. A statistically significant, albeit modest, positive correlation was found between the preference for work experience and the likelihood of applicants being hired, as well as between the preference for educational background and employment probability. These findings indicate that job seekers could improve their employability by acquiring relevant work experience, suggesting that hiring practices might benefit from a greater emphasis on practical experience. However, the study acknowledged limitations, including the use of simple random sampling and the focus on the National Capital Region, which may constrain the generalizability of the results to broader contexts.

Conclusions

In recent years, extensive research in human resource management has focused on understanding the preferred employment qualifications of human resource practitioners during recruitment and selection processes. This research has particularly examined the relative importance of various qualifications—such as knowledge, skills, abilities, and other characteristics— including educational background, skill sets, work experience, and personal attributes. While a significant body of literature emphasized the impact of work experience on predicting an applicant's performance and effectiveness within an organization (EPS, 2016; Pollard, 2019; NACE, 2020; Yendrey, 2021; Shakhshir, 2022; Tien, 2022; Monster, n.d.), some studies argued that work experience alone is not a reliable predictor of success (Glazer, 2017; Iddekinge et al., 2019; Beard, 2019; Heller, 2019). Conversely, other research suggests that both educational background and work experience are valued by employers (Becker, 1964; Pelta, 2021; U.S. Census Bureau, n.d.; Monster, n.d.).

The findings of this study revealed a low positive correlation between employers' preference for work experience and the likelihood of applicants' employability, as well as between preference for educational background and hiring probability. Significant differences were observed between these preferences and hiring outcomes. The study even highlighted the importance of both qualifications in recruitment, suggesting that employers should consider a broad range of attributes beyond just education or experience. The implications of this research extend to both job seekers and employers, providing insights into the relative value of work experience and educational background in hiring decisions, and offering a reference for future studies assessing these factors.

Therefore, it is recommended that employers adopt a more holistic approach in their recruitment processes by integrating a diverse set of candidate attributes beyond work experience and educational background. Given the observed low positive correlations between these qualifications and employability, employers should consider evaluating additional factors such as skills, competencies, and personal attributes when assessing job applicants. This comprehensive evaluation approach can provide a more accurate prediction of an applicant's potential performance and suitability for the role. Additionally, it is recommended that future research explore the interplay of various qualifications and attributes in greater depth to refine hiring practices and enhance understanding of their impact on job placement outcomes. For job seekers, developing a balanced portfolio of qualifications, including both relevant experience and educational credentials, may increase their competitiveness in the job market.

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